

Original Research

Foreign Entrepreneur Success in China: The Role of Entrepreneurial Cognition in Opportunity Recognition

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Abstract

There is a huge opportunity for foreign entrepreneurs to enter the Chinese market. They have noted that the market is difficult to enter and complex to navigate. This study contributes towards filling this gap by identifying the critical success factors for foreigners in China, basing on entrepreneurial cognition and opportunity recognition theories. 128 entrepreneurs in China were surveyed through semi-structured interviews. Their responses were collated and analyzed using graph theoretic matrix approach to identify and rank the factors with the most influence on their business success. The factors with the greatest influence on the success of foreign entrepreneurs are government policies and funding. Government policies towards innovation through financing for technology companies and the demographic make-up of the consumer population provide the greatest opportunities for foreigners. By understanding the most crucial success factors and the role of cognition in opportunity recognition, entrepreneurs and managers can derive meaningful insights into strategic choices regarding doing business in China. This study addresses a grossly under-researched topic of global entrepreneurs in China. Not only is there a large number of foreigners living in China, but they also find great difficulty in adjusting to the cultural scene and this affects business outcomes. Furthermore, GTMA is a highly scientific method that the authors show is valuable in social science research, particularly entrepreneurship research

Keywords: China, International entrepreneur, cognition, opportunity recognition.

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Introduction

China's entrepreneurship scene is one of the largest and most profitable in the world. Together, both Chinese and foreign entrepreneurs contribute over 60% of the country's GDP, are responsible for 80% of urban development and contribute 50% of fiscal revenues and taxes (He, Lu, & Qian, 2019; Huang, Liu, & Li, 2016). They can foster sustained economic growth through innovation (Qian, 2017) and currently tech entrepreneurs alone account for 41.49% of the total GDP (Shan, Jia, Zheng, & Xu, 2018). The Chinese government is well aware of the efficacy of entrepreneurship such that several macro-level strategies have been implemented to support and encourage entrepreneurship at every level.

There were approximately 556 262 foreign enterprises in China as of 2018, which accounts for 14.2% of the total number of entrepreneurs in China (B. I. Park & Xiao, 2021). While they are only a small portion of the total market, foreign entrepreneurs have advantages in capital technology, large profits and brand recognition that makes them a special group that the Chinese government hopes to attract more of through incentives and preferential taxes (Xu, Pan, Wu, & Yim, 2006). According to the Ministry of Commerce the investments for foreign invested enterprises (FIEs) rose steadily by an average 13% annually and were valued at 10 billion USD in Shanghai alone (K. Li, Zhang, Wang, Jiang, & Zhang, 2021). A study done by McKinsey in 2020 found that FIEs have the highest profit margins in the country at 2200 USD per employee (Bick, Chang, Wang, & Yu, 2020). Being a foreign entrepreneur is highly lucrative in what is one of the most prominent markets in the world. In 2018 alone, there were 60 553 new foreign enterprises registered with a cumulative 134.97 billion USD invested (MofCom, 2018).

Unfortunately, the market is just as difficult to enter as it is attractive. Extensive literature spanning over 25 years maps out the difficulties that entrepreneurs in China have faced, particularly, foreign entrepreneurs (Lee, 2003). These include complex and inconsistently applied laws, national isolation that has created a closed business and social ecosystem, unique cultural context, language deficiencies and rigorous competition from domestic players and copycat products, conflicts in managerial and cultural integration, lack of access to network resources or "guanxi" and multi-layered distribution channels, liability of foreignness, and corruption in public services (Y. Chang & Hu, 2020; Karakaya & Stahl, 1989; Lee, 2003; Min & Chen, 2003; Niu, Dong, & Chen, 2012; W. Zhang & Zhai, 2016; Zhou, 2012).

According to entrepreneurial cognition theory a unique outlook held by an entrepreneur allows them to objectively evaluate their personal strengths and advantages that are relevant to their business, which is invaluable in international entrepreneurship (Pellegrini & Ciappei, 2015). This means that the ability of a foreign entrepreneur to navigate a unique environment, learn from experiences and make good strategic decisions largely depends on their knowledge-cognition perspective. It also means that entrepreneurial cognition has a direct impact on firm strategies, opportunity identification through information processing and therefore directly affects entrepreneurial successes (L. Yang, 2015).

Despite the large number of foreign enterprises in China (MofCom, 2018), there is only little literature that focuses on foreign entrepreneurs specifically (Ahlstrom, Young, Nair, & Law, 2003; Gurău, Dana, & Katz-Volovelsky, 2020; Lightfoot & Almeida, 2007). Though many previous studies explain the policies and theories regarding the opportunities for foreign entrepreneurs in China (Ahlstrom & Ding, 2015; Anwar & Sun, 2015; Wu & Burge, 2018; Y. Zhang, Zhao, & Ge, 2016), there still exists a gap in the literature in understanding what is the nature of the different factors that foreign entrepreneurs have to face. To this end, the first contribution of this study will be to provide a clear picture of the dynamic environment that foreign entrepreneurs are facing in China's business ecosystem, from the perspective of the entrepreneurs.

There are studies that have mapped the difficulty that foreign entrepreneurs have in new markets (Dickson, Yao, & Hill, 2020; Hamizah, 2020; Liu, Al Asady, & Fu, 2020), but we found only one done in China. China is a very unique case study. Arribas, Hernández, and Vila (2013) stated that China is very different from other economies of similar size and status because it has a dynamic business environment which is still taking shape. It is quickly becoming a world leader, it's the second largest economy in the world and also a major player in global and regional economic blocks. The challenges that foreigners need to overcome here are not easily comparable to any other market. It is also a highly -sought after market and this therefore makes it an intriguing case. Furthermore, the economic, social and political development in different regions of the country is imbalanced. Location, therefore, is likely a decisive factor in the success of FIEs. (Luo & Lemański, 2016; Puslecki, Trapczynski, & Staszaków, 2016). This study will address current questions regarding the context for entrepreneurship on emerging economies that have a dynamic environment which is at a formative stage, more so for people who are not native to those countries.

The ability of entrepreneurs to identify the challenges and opportunities in China is largely influenced by their experience, background and a myriad of other personal factors (Si, Zhang, & Teng, 2021). Furthermore, the role of foreign entrepreneurs in China has been changing over the past few years on account of developing institutional frameworks, entrepreneurship policies and the regional differences in openness. There is also a gap identified by Ng and Fu (2018) that there is a need to understand how cultural differences affect entrepreneurship. Basing our investigation on entrepreneurial cognition theory, the second contribution of this study is to explore what factors affect the success of foreign entrepreneurs in China, whether if and how these factors are interrelated? This will be achieved through answering these questions: "What factors influence the opportunity recognition by foreign entrepreneurs" and "Are there any interdependencies amongst these factors?".

To answer these questions, we employ a qualitative exploratory research method to capture a more holistic view of the business environment that foreigners in China encounter which is more comprehensive than existing studies that focus on the singular point of view (Gurău et al., 2020; Lightfoot & Almeida, 2007). It would allow for the investigation of environmental dynamics both situational and action oriented (R. Mitchell, Randolph-Seng, & Mitchell, 2011) that are difficult to single out but largely influence the knowledge-cognition perspective of entrepreneurs. For this reason, the third contribution of this paper will be to test graph theory and matrix approach (GTMA) as a

suitable method for undertaking entrepreneurship research. It has successfully been used in other fields of social science including organizational management (Gurumurthy, Mazumdar, & Muthusubramanian, 2013), logistics and supply chain management (Agrawal, Singh, & Murtaza, 2016; Gupta & Singh, 2015) as well as management science (Harary, 1959). This method can account for the bi-directional inter-relationships amongst the main factors and examine to what extent each of them affects the business outcomes of entrepreneurial activities in a way that other methods cannot. The study will go on to outline a literature review of previous studies in section 2, define the variables based on a combination of priori research and consultation of experts in section 3, build and calculate the graph theoretic model in section 4 and discuss the results and research implications in section 5.

Literature Review

Foreign Entrepreneurship in China

Entrepreneurship is the creative process of monetizing problem-solving methods (Ahlstrom & Ding, 2015; Alvarez, Barney, & Anderson, 2013). The entrepreneur is therefore the one who changes a market or economic system through provision of an innovative product or business model often in response to a valuable economic opportunity (Devi, 2020). China's "mass entrepreneurship and innovation" policies are attractive to entrepreneurs and they offer lucrative opportunities for them. A foreigner is defined by the (CambridgeDictionary) as a person who comes from another country. In this context it describes people who hold nationalities outside of Chinese territories. With over 840 000 foreigners living in China (NBS, 2021), of which 9% are entrepreneurs or business owners, the study must stipulate the difference between small business owners and entrepreneurs.

The entrepreneurs, that are the focus of this study, have an entrepreneurial spirit, are innovative in creating new markets, new products, new organization structure and methods of production and service delivery (Ng & Fu, 2018; Urban, Van Vuuren, & Barreira, 2008). Entrepreneurial activity among foreigners has been on the rise in recent years across the country (Ashourizadeh, Li, & Wickstrøm, 2020) but they are clearly skewed between geographical regions. Eastern coastal regions are far more developed than the central and western regions. Eastern China has significantly better infrastructure, favorable implementation of national and provincial policies for regional entrepreneurship and therefore gives better opportunities (M. Li, He, & Zhao, 2020). Most foreigners live in Tier One cities across the country. However, there still are some discrepancies between these cities such as Shanghai in Eastern China, Guangzhou and Shenzhen in the South, Beijing in the North and Chengdu in the West. There is need to find the differences between the success of foreign entrepreneurs in the different economic zones of China.

Going further, what really defines success to an entrepreneur? Wach, Stephan, Marjan, and Wegge (2018) connote that unlike managers, entrepreneurs measure their performance against their goals. So instead of pegging success with survival, return on assets, number of employees and market share; entrepreneurs measure performance and success based on self-actualization (Benzing, Chu, & Kara, 2009), independence and

autonomy over firms (Stephan, Hart, & Drews, 2015), social contribution, personal fulfillment (E. St-Jean & Audet, 2012) and work-life balance (É. St-Jean & Duhamel, 2020). Their success can be grouped into business-oriented and personal-oriented. The former encompasses financial and also development of innovation capacity and enhanced status (Lukes & Stephan, 2012) while the latter entails relationships formed (Sydler, Haefliger, & Pruksa, 2014) and value of the impact of innovation on the community (Wach, Stephan, & Gorgievski, 2016). This paper espouses these as the successes which entrepreneurs in China will be aiming for.

Theories of Entrepreneurship

This study is based largely on Entrepreneurial Cognition and Opportunity Recognition Theory.

Entrepreneurship literature has recently devoted much attention to understanding how entrepreneurs think and why they make the choices they make. Significant attention has been given to understanding the thought structures and knowledge used by individuals to assess situations, take decisions and act on these to recognize opportunities and grow new (Ronald K. Mitchell, Smith, Seawright, & Morse, 2000; Ronald K. Mitchell et al., 2002; B. Randolph-Seng et al., 2015). Entrepreneurship cognition is the ability of an entrepreneur to identify and successfully act on opportunities in a dynamic environment in which others find it difficult to do so (Shepherd & Patzelt, 2018). Entrepreneurial behavior is influenced by these mental or cognitive processes. For this reason, a strand of literature that seeks to study entrepreneurship from this cognitive aspect has emerged to investigate the mechanism through which an individual obtains, processes and utilizes information.

In the entrepreneurial cognition handbook (J. R. Mitchell, Mitchell, & Randolph-Seng, 2014), it is described that entrepreneurs operate in uncertain market conditions and because of this they need to make use of both situation and action-oriented cognition. The former is the knowledge which is inseparable from the context in which it is learned and is largely connected to culture, home country and social background. The latter is the way in which the entrepreneur observes and reacts to objects and concepts. Together, these multi-level dynamics are processed by the entrepreneurs leading to the emergence of new enterprises and realization of new opportunities in a particular region and with special competitive advantage (Sanchez, Carballo, & Gutiérrez, 2011; Sarasvathy & Dew, 2011).

In the context of foreign entrepreneurship, individuals can make use of the special opportunities that arise in dynamic environments and attain significant profits. The cognition perspective is the degree to which the entrepreneur can make use of their personal knowledge and experience to identify what is relevant to their business. It explains global strategic choices of entrepreneurs in international entrepreneurship by showing the relationship between external environment and internal information (Pellegrini & Ciappei, 2015). This can be seen by entrepreneurs who operate in the same external environments but achieve different results (L. Yang, 2015). The social context shapes the strategic decisions of entrepreneurs (Sasseti, Marzi, Cavaliere, & Ciappei, 2018). Entrepreneurial cognition, therefore, has an effect on entrepreneurial success as it bridges the relationship between organizational strategy and market information

processing. Raza, Muffatto, and Saeed (2018) found that entrepreneurial cognition mediates the relationships between prevailing institutional environments and new venture creation by individuals. J. S. C. Randolph-Seng and Atinc (2020) describe how many studies on entrepreneurship have focused on individuals rather than the interactions amongst those individuals in a more contextualized sense. This study therefore hopes to contribute towards filling this gap by studying these interactions between the entrepreneurs and their environment in the context of an emerging economy.

Venkataraman (2019) connotes that the most important skill for an entrepreneur to have is the ability to identify opportunities. Urbano, Audretsch, Aparicio, and Noguera (2019) explain how existing regulative statutes and cultural norms of China affect foreigners doing business there. Embedded within this institutional framework is opportunity recognition theory (Phillips & Tracey, 2007). Foreign entrepreneurs must be able to recognize the opportunities that exist for them in line with provisions made by the institutions. Institutions will present the environment that foreigners must encounter. Formal institutions regulated by the State determine the prevailing state of entrepreneurship (North, 1991) in China. They determine the foreign entrepreneur's ability to operate, to obtain legal residence status and visas as well as which industries to enter. This means the formal institutions in China enable as well as constrain entrepreneurs. Social interactions and observation of culture and language are so important and are a determinant of the success or failure of a business in terms of productivity and formality (Lee, 2003).

Entrepreneurial Cognition- Opportunity recognition nexus

The relationship between the entrepreneurs internal thought processes and the external environment is indeed a cutting-edge strand of literature in recent years (York & Venkataraman, 2010; Zanella, Solano, Hallam, & Guda, 2019). It can clarify the strategic choices made by entrepreneurs in the same environment to take advantage of different opportunities and create different ventures. While (Ahlstrom & Ding) together with other relevant literature on foreign entrepreneurship in China have detailed the challenges and even opportunities for foreigners in China, almost no paper to the best of our knowledge has investigated how the cognition experience of entrepreneurs affects their outcomes. The unique circumstance that foreign entrepreneurs operate in a regulative grey area in China in which the government is a stakeholder makes for an intriguing case study because aspects that one individual may perceive as a challenge would equally be perceived as an opportunity by a different individual. Entrepreneurial cognition and opportunity recognition theories collide at a fascinating nexus in this case of a dynamic environment with wildly varied cultural and socio-economic differences within a single country. This study further seeks to look into the controversial performance measurement of FIEs that stems from foreign enterprises reportedly having larger profit margins despite having lower capacities than Chinese counterparts (Qi, Wu, Wang, & Wang, 2021; Xu et al., 2006). This study therefore follows the theoretical framework in Figure 1.

Fig1. Conceptual Diagram

Conceptual Development

Item generation

In order to understand the circumstance of foreign entrepreneurship in China, an initial review of studies on the market entry barriers (MEBs) of entrepreneurs in China was done to compile the prominent factors that affect the business environment for foreign entrepreneurs (Jayaraman, 2010; Niu et al., 2012; W. Zhang & Zhai, 2016). This study gathered findings from the literature survey on MEB's dating back from 1989-2020 (Fan & Zhang, 2017; Kloosterman, 2010; Lee, 2003; Niu et al., 2012; Raeesi, Dastranj, Mohammadi, & Rasouli, 2013; Steinz, Van Rijnsoever, & Nauta, 2016). The paper by Dickson et al. (2020) was used as a basis on the groupings of the items. A preliminary list of 30 items divided into 6 general categories (5 items for each).

Expert Review

Four experts who are senior academics in Entrepreneurship, Business Administration and Management studies and have experience working with foreign entrepreneurs at Chinese universities provided us with suggestions and feedback on the face validity of the 30 items. They were emailed the list of items along with the title of the manuscript and objectives of the study. Accounting for their feedback, we reworded some of the items, combined those that were ultimately the same and deleted 4 items. This resulted in a set of 20 items divided into 5 clusters namely Chinese Government Policy (*GP*), national Demographics (*DG*), Domestic Market Competition (*MC*), Local Business Relations (*BR*) and access to Funding (*Fu*).

Nomological Validity

Government Policy (GP)

Arguably, government policy is the most powerful shaping force of the business environment in China (Woetzel et al., 2014). Firstly, the Open-Door Policy (GP1) from 1979 saw China open up its borders to investment from other countries. This has since

led to the State decentralizing decision-making regarding trade, opening of special economic zones in strategic locations to facilitate it, loosened control on foreign exchange and replacement of administrative restrictions with tariffs and quotas (S. H. Park & Ungson, 2016; S. H. Park, Ungson, & Zhou, 2013). This has significantly transformed the nation to a market economy. Secondly, China is forex-controlled meaning companies must apply for foreign exchange certificate and review annually by supplying documents for all money coming in and out of China through business transactions (Ji-yun, 2002) (GP2). Although the circulation of foreign currency is prohibited, The Shanghai Pilot FTZ currently allows full convertibility of RMB, the beginning of the relaxation of this policy (Deloitte, 2017). Thirdly, in many 1st and 2nd tier cities, the State Tax Administration has introduced some attractive incentives for foreign entrepreneurs and startups (Hsu, Lee, Leon-Gonzalez 2018) that give preferential tax treatment and substantial tax holidays (GP3). In certain industries, such as high-new-tech-enterprises (HNTEs) and cities in Guangdong and west China, they are offering a 2-year tax holiday followed by 3 years of 12.5% income tax versus the documented 25%. Therefore, entrepreneurs can easily bear the tax load after 5 years giving them enough time to get their businesses up and running (Deloitte, 2017). Finally, the last aspect of this is the regulatory transparency of policies regarding investment (GP4). Jayaraman (2010) describes the legal system as “loosely defined” allowing for many loopholes alongside red tape and misinformation. Entrepreneurs with a good network of Chinese colleagues will have less difficulty navigating simple tasks such as permits and approvals, however without these connections one will face grave difficulties navigating the red tape and run-around as well as may have no protection against theft of expertise and intellectual property (IP) (Tung & Cho, 2000).

Demographics (DG)

China’s large population is a great opportunity for entrepreneurs but some of the specific demographic properties make it a complicated love story. China has a fast-growing wealthy middle class (DG1) as more rural workers move to urban areas for better paid jobs and native Chinese business people expand and have greater disposable income (S. H. Park & Ungson, 2016). These consumers have higher demands for quality and efficiency than ever before and their needs are dynamic. Chinese consumers spent CNY 34.8 trillion in 2018 alone (NBSC, 2019), a figure expected to rise to CNY 60 trillion by 2025; therefore their complex needs dictate how businesses will operate (Farrell, Gersch, & Stephenson, 2006). Chinese Mandarin is the standard language spoken in China (DG2). Although many young workers in big cities will be able to speak English, most of other business conversations with officials, sponsors and partners will be in Chinese (Cui & Kwon, 2014). Therefore, though not compulsory, foreign entrepreneurs who can communicate in Chinese to their counter parts are more likely to gain the trust of others (Chua, Ingram, & Morris, 2008). Innovation management (DG3) is very important for domestic and foreign entrepreneurs in China. Previously, it was primarily foreign firms that introduced new products from their countries into China through partnerships (Collinson & Liu, 2019) with local companies but now has shifted to companies independently innovating to create products unique and original to Chinese tastes. It is crucial that entrepreneurs settling in China study the market and have significant competitive products and services tailored for the market specifically. This gives rise to another aspect, the digitized society (DG4). Verot (2018) stated that Chinese

consumers chat, shop, order groceries, pay for services, watch television and even date online, meaning whatever business model entrepreneurs will choose, having an online infrastructure is invaluable.

Business Relations (BR)

The CEO of Nexcelia Solutions (Munganyi, 2020); an entrepreneur with a tech startup in Shanghai; said “In China business is more of a relationship than a transaction”. This is embedded in the 5000-year history of the country. People place great importance on networking and “social capital” because who you know can be gateway to better opportunities for your business. This social capital is often termed “Guanxi”(BR1). Yau, Lee, Chow, Sin, and Alan (2000) make it clear that cultivating long term profitable relationships is a worthwhile social investment. Guanxi can also be looked at from a long-term angle as “trust” (BR2). By conducting a series of transactions successfully over some time (Trimarchi, Liesch, & Tamaschke, 2010) , people will come to trust your expertise and you will be given opportunities based on recommendations and testimonials given on your behalf. Being outsiders, often from different races and cultures, foreign entrepreneurs will need to gain the trust of customers and suppliers alike and overcome the liability of foreignness (Ikegami, Maznevski, & Ota, 2017). Gaining trust, especially in Joint Venture and Partnership companies, may require foreign companies to share their technological know-how and IP with local firms which has given rise to the unfortunate copycat culture “Shanzhai” (BR3). Although the government is increasing measures in recent years with special committees to hear IP protection suits (Hennessy, 2012), there is still a significant threat in terms of counterfeit goods and theft of intellectual property for reproduction (Jiang & Shan, 2016). One of the most attractive aspects of China used to be the cheap labor cost. However, in recent years, it has lost its luster as a base for cheap manufacturing (D. T. Yang, Chen, & Monarch, 2010). In 2018 ,58.52% of the population was living in urban areas, earning a national average minimum wage of 74,318 yuan, almost double the 36,539 yuan earned in 2010 (NBSC, 2010, 2019). The increase in labor cost (BR4) is not conducive to competitiveness and the cost of operating is increasingly higher by the year as are the expert needs of firms (Wang, Kinnucan, & Duffy, 2019; Zheng, Zhao, & Li, 2019).

Market competition (MC)

In 2010 when China released its 12th FYP document, it stated it was no longer content with being “the worlds factory” and rather wanted to move to an innovation economy (Worldwide, 2010). This means many domestic companies (MC1) especially in the emerging industries of high-end technology compete fiercely. Foreign entrepreneurs in these industries will be disadvantaged in that they don’t have the vast supply network and government funding that these firms will have (Buysse & Essers, 2019) but will have to perform equally well if not better in order to stay in business. Froese, Sutherland, Lee, Liu, and Pan (2019) make it clear that state financed firms often have many legal and regulatory advantages over foreign entrepreneur firms. Some American and Europeans have expressed feeling “stonewalled” in China, that is being given unfair access to the market (MC2) as the government gears towards its “Made in China 2025” initiative and shows some form of preference for Chinese firms over foreign ones (V. K. Chang & Pieke, 2018). Another obstacle for the foreign entrepreneur who wishes to open a firm in

China, especially WFOE, is the limited access to the supply chain (MC3). The entrepreneur will need to begin networking and creating his own system of suppliers, customers, distributors and retailers (Buysse & Essers, 2019) which will require a lot of valuable time that competitors will be gaining. In this process one will need to invest in a well-connected human resource (MC4), either through “buying guanxi” by hiring already well-connected staff or spend a lot of time networking to meet and gain the friendship of officials and other business people (Yen & Abosag, 2016) in order to gain an edge in market and financial performance and can reduce the liability of foreignness (Ikegami et al., 2017).

Funding (Fu)

One of the biggest questions for entrepreneurs is where they will get money to start their businesses and this applies the same in China. Blachman (2018) describes how Chinese venture capitalists (VCs) are looking to invest in foreign bred startups that have highly advanced engineering and data science as well as hard technology skills (Fu1). Such companies that pass the bar will be given access to major players in China to collaborate with, making it an even more attractive to be funded by Chinese VCs. The private equity (PE) market in China is slightly less developed than that of American and European countries (Nazareno, Zhou, & You, 2019) (Fu2). Though also available to foreigner entrepreneurs Lerner and Schoar (2005) suggest that there is still ambiguity in the legal environment and as a result PE manager sometimes buy controlling stakes earlier on in the business leaving the actual entrepreneur with weaker decision-making authority (Kaplan & Stromberg, 2009). Another funding option is that of self-organized foreign entrepreneurs (Fu3) that is to say foreigners that will use their own funds sourced from personal savings, friends and family. However according to the interviews conducted with foreign entrepreneurs in China, self-financed entrepreneurs with less than 5 million RMB are limited and stand a risk of hemorrhaging cash and failing within 3-5 years (Ng & Fu, 2018), while most foreign startups need at least 5-7 years to settle down. Lastly due to a high interest in HNTes (Fu4) in China, in cities such as Shanghai, Shenzhen and Chengdu there are possibilities of getting startup capital (\$148,800) and 3 years rent free in designated technology zones (Bo, 2019). Business incubation programs are increasingly popular as well and offer many financial and other resources crucial for start-ups along with the support of the government and access to supply chains (Chandra & Fealey, 2009).

The factors presented here have intricate interrelationships amongst them and some depend on each other. This is shown in the following conceptual model can be drawn up in Figure 2.

The resultant cause and effect diagram of all these factors is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Cause and Effect Diagram

Figure 3. Behavioral digraph

While the literature and theories describe and explain the factors that affect foreign entrepreneurs in China, it still remains unclear to what extent these factors influence business environment in which the foreign entrepreneur and how they interact with one another. The following section explore the inter-relationships of the subfactors operating within the major factors as well as explore the nexus points of each of these factors with one another to determine the degree to which they impact the success of foreign entrepreneurs.

Research Design

The investigation made use of graph-theoretic matrix approach (GTMA) to examine interdependencies amongst the factors and determine the most critical ones. Characteristics of this technique are its ability to capture the interdependencies and hierarchical structure amongst variables from a considerably small sample size. This study specifically elected GTMA as the most appropriate method because collecting large amounts of data is notoriously difficult in China so it was better to collect a small amount of real data (Riege, 2003; Trimarchi et al., 2010). Furthermore, it allows for qualitative inductive research whereby it is possible to formulate conclusions based on the results of the data rather than analyzing data based on existing theories (Fang, Tung, Berg, & Nematshahi, 2017). Graph theory is a simple and formidable technique which is free from these limitations and has in fact proved its fortitude in every field of study (Muduli, Govindan, Barve, & Geng, 2013).

The most common representation of the graph is by means of diagrams in which vertices are represented as points and each edge as a line segment joining its end vertices. GTMA has 3 constituents i) diagraph representation for visual analysis ii) matrix representation valuable for computer processing iii) permanent representation suitable for expressing the effect of each variable by a single number (Grover, Agrawal, & Khan, 2004). To get the permanent value of each variable the indexes of multi-nominals must be computed and subjected to comparison and classification by certain criterion in this case, importance, leading to an election of the best value. The concept of a permanent matrix and performance attributes index gives correct and complete evaluation of the data. It allows the selection of the most suitable option and evaluate the overall quality of the industry.

Following this, the permanent matrices of critical factors were drawn-up and used to analyze the intensity of each critical factor and rank them according to importance in influence and opportunity for foreigners hoping to do business in China and what they may face in entering the market. The authors made use of GTMA to examine interdependencies amongst the factor and draw out the most critical ones.

Data Collection

The items concluded on by the literature review and experts' review were used to formulate questions for semi-structured interview questions that were asked foreign entrepreneurs in China. A qualitative approach was chosen because the study aimed to understand the views and experiences of the respondents. For this reason, structured questions were sent to the respondents before the interview time and they were encouraged to prepare and conduct the interview as a narration (Fang et al., 2017). The researchers also made use of follow-up probing questions to better understand the respondents (Abubakar, Anasori, & Lasisi, 2019). All the interviews were conducted through a mix of video calls, telephone calls and face to face meetings according to accessibility and each lasted between 45 minutes to one hour. They were recorded and transcribed afterwards. The transcribed were combed for recurring items and key words which were noted down and slowly regrouped into same or similar clusters of words and phrases. These clusters were further refined and finally made into the individual variables,

where weightage was based on frequency and context in the interviews. Main questions focused on the principal objective of the study: challenges faced in doing business in China. Other questions also probed on the subthemes of the research: industry specific challenges and opportunities, the role of the Chinese government and business regulations as well as the state of local consumers and market competition.

Sampling

Responses were gathered from a total of 128 foreign entrepreneurs, from 42 countries, spread across 7 major regions of China and 13 industries. We employed a purposive snowball sampling technique according to the method used by (Karadal, Shneikat, Abubakar, & Bhatti, 2020) . Established and experienced foreign entrepreneurs living and operating ventures in China were selected, starting with ones that the researchers had from personal contacts. These were asked to recommend future respondents from their social networks, personal contacts and industry acquaintances. From a total of 130 contacts we had, we received 128 valid responses. A 98% response rate for a snowball sample is considered to be valid (Karadal et al., 2020). These were urged to express their views and opinions on the topic. The entrepreneurs were distributed as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of entrepreneurs that were sampled

North China	North-East China	East China	South China	Central China	South-West China	North-west China
Tianjin Communication & IT (6)	Jilin Retail (3)	Shanghai Automobile (8), Foodstuff (12), EdTech (6), Personal care products (4)	Guangdong Home appliances (9), Apparel (5), Logistics (1)	Hubei Retail (2), Personal care products (2)	Chongqing Agriculture (1), Logistics (1)	Shaanxi- Agriculture (1)
Beijing EdTech (10)		Jiangsu Textiles (14), Communication & IT (6)	Shenzhen- Electronics (5)	Henan- Electronics (4), Food stuff (2)	Sichuan- Foodstuff (2)	
		Fujian Apparel (9)				
		Zhejiang Toys (4), Household appliances (4), Furniture (5)				

Model Construction and Calibration

From the conceptual model, 5 major factors with 4 subfactors each can be derived, namely Government Policy (GP), Demographics (DG), Market Competition (MC),

Business Relations (BR) and Funding (Fu), giving a total of 20 items. All the variables are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2: List of Variables

Government Policy (GP)	Demographics (DG)	Business Relations (BR)	Market Competition (MC)	Funding (Fu)
GP1: Open Door Policy	DG1: Upcoming middle class	BR1: Guanxi	MC1: Domestic Competitors	Fu1: Venture Capital
GP2: Forex Policy	DG2: Language	BR2: Trust	MC2: Market Access Restriction	Fu2: Private Equity
GP3: Tax Obligations	DG3: Innovation Management	BR3: IPR	MC3: Access to supply networks	Fu3: Self Organized Entrepreneurs
GP4: Regulatory Transparency	DG4: Digitized Society	BR4: Rising labor costs	MC4: Human resource and Political connections	Fu4: Tech-Startups

The behavioral diagraph (also called the directed graph) is prepared to represent the behavioral factors critical to the success of foreign entrepreneurs in terms of nodes and edges. Nodes will stand for the major factors (C_i) while the edges will show their interactions (f_{ij}). Figure 3 illustrates the behavioral factors and interactions amongst the 5 major factors C_1 C_2 C_3 C_4 and C_5 .

Table 3: Relative importance of factor f_{ij}

Class description	Relative importance of Attributes	
	F_{ij}	$f_{ji} = 10 - F_{ij}$
Both factors are equally important	5	5
One factor is slightly important	6	4
One factor is very important over the other	7	3
One factor is most important over the other	8	2
One factor is extremely important over the other	9	1
One factor is exceptionally important over the other	10	0

Similarly, Figure 4 shows the corresponding nodes and edges for the subfactors of the major factor GP. The nodes denoted C_1^1 C_2^1 C_3^1 and C_4^1 represent the subfactors GP1, GP2, GP3 and GP4 while the edges f_{ij} indicated the interdependencies among the subfactors that affect the success of foreign entrepreneurs in China.

Fig 4: Behavioral digraph for one factor , Government Policy (GP)

Data Analysis

The above digraphs (Figure 3 and Figure 4) give a visual analysis of the relationships amongst the variables and are represented in equation 1 by a 5X5 matrix for the overall critical success factors (CSF) and 4X4 matrices represented in equations 2,3,4,5 and 6 for the sub-factors in each.

$$CSF = \begin{pmatrix} C_1 & f_{12} & f_{13} & f_{14} & f_{15} \\ f_{21} & C_2 & f_{23} & f_{24} & f_{25} \\ f_{31} & f_{32} & C_3 & f_{34} & f_{35} \\ f_{41} & f_{42} & f_{43} & C_4 & f_{45} \\ f_{51} & f_{52} & f_{53} & f_{54} & C_5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where CSF is the Critical Success Factors index. C_i stands for the major factors (GP=C1, DG=C2, BR=C3, MC=C4, Fu=C5) found on nodes of the digraphs and f_{ij} is the relative importance of the i th factor as compared to the j th which are shows as edges in the digraph.

$$Permanent(C_1) = per(GP) = \begin{pmatrix} C_1^1 & f_{12}^1 & f_{13}^1 & f_{14}^1 \\ f_{21}^1 & C_2^1 & f_{23}^1 & f_{24}^1 \\ f_{31}^1 & f_{32}^1 & C_3^1 & f_{34}^1 \\ f_{41}^1 & f_{42}^1 & f_{43}^1 & C_4^1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In equation 2 where $C_1^1, C_2^1, C_3^1, C_4^1$ stand for the subfactors GP1, GP2, GP3 and GP4.

$$Permanent(C_2) = per(DG) = \begin{pmatrix} C_1^2 & f_{12}^2 & f_{13}^2 & f_{14}^2 \\ f_{21}^2 & C_2^2 & f_{23}^2 & f_{24}^2 \\ f_{31}^2 & f_{32}^2 & C_3^2 & f_{34}^2 \\ f_{41}^2 & f_{42}^2 & f_{43}^2 & C_4^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In equation 3 where $C_1^2, C_2^2, C_3^2, C_4^2$ stand for the subfactors DG1, DG2, DG3 and DG4.

$$\text{Permanent}(C_3) = \text{per}(\text{BR}) = \begin{pmatrix} C_1^3 & f_{12}^3 & f_{13}^3 & f_{14}^3 \\ f_{21}^3 & C_2^3 & f_{23}^3 & f_{24}^3 \\ f_{31}^3 & f_{32}^3 & C_3^3 & f_{34}^3 \\ f_{41}^3 & f_{42}^3 & f_{43}^3 & C_4^3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In equation 4 where $C_1^3, C_2^3, C_3^3, C_4^3$ stand for the subfactors BR1, BR2, BR3 and BR4.

$$\text{Permanent}(C_4) = \text{per}(\text{MC}) = \begin{pmatrix} C_1^4 & f_{12}^4 & f_{13}^4 & f_{14}^4 \\ f_{21}^4 & C_2^4 & f_{23}^4 & f_{24}^4 \\ f_{31}^4 & f_{32}^4 & C_3^4 & f_{34}^4 \\ f_{41}^4 & f_{42}^4 & f_{43}^4 & C_4^4 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

In equation 5 where $C_1^4, C_2^4, C_3^4, C_4^4$ stand for the subfactors MC1, MC2, MC3 and MC4.

$$\text{Permanent}(C_5) = \text{per}(\text{Fu}) = \begin{pmatrix} C_1^5 & f_{12}^5 & f_{13}^5 & f_{14}^5 \\ f_{21}^5 & C_2^5 & f_{23}^5 & f_{24}^5 \\ f_{31}^5 & f_{32}^5 & C_3^5 & f_{34}^5 \\ f_{41}^5 & f_{42}^5 & f_{43}^5 & C_4^5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In equation 6 where $C_1^5, C_2^5, C_3^5, C_4^5$ stand for the subfactors Fu1, Fu2, Fu3 and Fu4.

Permanent representation

The Jukart-Ryser formula used to mathematically explain the permanent function is illustrated in equation 7 as follows:

$$\left[\prod_{i=1}^5 C_i + \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k \sum_l f_{ij} f_{ji} f_{kl} f_{lk} + \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k \sum_l (f_{ij} f_{jk} f_{kl} f_{li} + f_{ji} f_{il} f_{lk} f_{kj} f_{ij}) + \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k (f_{ij} f_{ji} \times (f_{kl} f_{lk}) + \sum_j \sum_i \sum_k \sum_l (f_{ij} f_{jk} f_{kl} f_{li} + f_{il} f_{lk} f_{kj} f_{ji})) \right] \quad (7)$$

The permanent expression contains values of (n+1) grouping. Each factor has 4 subfactors, n=4, meaning there will be 5 groupings whose meaning is outlined as follows:

- The 1st group contains 1 term and represents the symbiotic relationships amongst the 5 major factors contributing to the success of foreign entrepreneurs in China, $C_1 C_2 C_3 C_4 C_5$.
- The 2nd grouping is absent because a self-loop does not exist in this model and was not depicted in the diagram
- The 3rd group has 2 terms and signifies two-factor interdependence (i.e., f_{ij}, f_{ji}) together with the remaining drivers (i.e., 2 in this case)
- The 4th group has 3 terms of each and represents three-drivers interdependence (i.e. f_{ij}, f_{jk}, f_{ki}) together with the remaining drivers (i.e., 1 in this case)

- The 5th group has two subgroupings i) a set of 2 two factor interdependence (i.e., f_{ij}, f_{ji} and f_{ik}, f_{ki}) together with the remaining drivers (i.e., 0 in this case) ii) a set of 4 factor interdependencies (i.e. $f_{ij}, f_{jk}, f_{kl}, f_{ji}$ and $f_{li}, f_{ik}, f_{kj}, f_{il}$) and the remaining drivers which is also 0.

In light of this, using the resultant matrix and permanent value for Government policy is:

$$\text{Per (GP)} = \begin{pmatrix} 8 & 7 & 6 & 6 \\ 3 & 4 & 4 & 4 \\ 4 & 6 & 5 & 5 \\ 4 & 6 & 5 & 6 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

explained by:

$$= C_1^1 C_2^1 C_3^1 C_4^1 + (f_{12}^1 f_{21}^1 f_3^1 C_4^1 + f_{13}^1 f_{31}^1 C_2^1 C_4^1 + f_{14}^1 f_{41}^1 C_2^1 C_3^1 + f_{23}^1 f_{32}^1 C_4^1 C_1^1 + f_{24}^1 f_{42}^1 C_1^1 C_3^1 + f_{34}^1 f_{43}^1 C_1^1 C_2^1) + (f_{23}^1 f_{34}^1 f_{42}^1 C_1^1 + f_{24}^1 f_{43}^1 f_{32}^1 C_1^1 + f_{13}^1 f_{34}^1 f_{41}^1 C_2^1 + f_{14}^1 f_{43}^1 f_{31}^1 C_2^1 + f_{12}^1 f_{24}^1 f_{41}^1 C_3^1 + f_{14}^1 f_{42}^1 f_{21}^1 C_3^1 + f_{12}^1 f_{23}^1 f_{31}^1 C_4^1 + f_{13}^1 f_{32}^1 f_{21}^1 C_4^1) + (f_{12}^1 f_{21}^1 f_{34}^1 f_{43}^1 + f_{13}^1 f_{31}^1 f_{24}^1 f_{42}^1 + f_{14}^1 f_{41}^1 f_{23}^1 f_{32}^1 + f_{12}^1 f_{23}^1 f_{34}^1 f_{41}^1 + f_{14}^1 f_{43}^1 f_{32}^1 f_{21}^1 + f_{13}^1 f_{34}^1 f_{42}^1 f_{21}^1 + f_{21}^1 f_{24}^1 f_{43}^1 f_{31}^1 + f_{14}^1 f_{42}^1 f_{23}^1 f_{31}^1 + f_{13}^1 f_{32}^1 f_{24}^1 f_{41}^1).$$

Substituting the numerical values as per the matrix, the next step is to calculate the permanent value of government policy as a factor contributing to the success of foreign entrepreneurs

$$8 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6 + (7 \times 3 \times 5 \times 6 + 6 \times 4 \times 2 \times 6 + 6 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5 + 4 \times 6 \times 8 \times 6 + 4 \times 6 \times 8 \times 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 8 \times 4) + (4 \times 5 \times 6 \times 8 + 4 \times 6 \times 5 \times 8 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 4 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 4 + 7 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 \times 6 \times 3 \times 5 + 7 \times 4 \times 4 \times 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 4 \times 6) + (7 \times 3 \times 5 \times 5 + 6 \times 4 \times 4 \times 6 + 6 \times 4 \times 4 \times 6 + 7 \times 3 \times 5 \times 4 + 6 \times 5 \times 6 \times 3 + 6 \times 5 \times 6 \times 3 + 7 \times 4 \times 5 \times 4 + 6 \times 6 \times 4 \times 4 + 6 \times 6 \times 4 \times 4) = 15\ 887.$$

Similarly, permanent values of other factors are calculated:

$$\text{Per (DG)} = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 8 & 6 & 7 \\ 2 & 5 & 5 & 8 \\ 4 & 5 & 5 & 6 \\ 3 & 2 & 4 & 6 \end{pmatrix} = 18\ 195 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Per (MC)} = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 7 & 6 & 5 \\ 3 & 3 & 8 & 3 \\ 4 & 2 & 2 & 6 \\ 5 & 7 & 4 & 4 \end{pmatrix} = 11\ 256 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Per (BR)} = \begin{pmatrix} 6 & 7 & 6 & 3 \\ 3 & 6 & 4 & 6 \\ 4 & 6 & 5 & 8 \\ 7 & 4 & 2 & 7 \end{pmatrix} = 13\ 306 \quad (5)$$

$$Per (Fu) = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 7 & 8 & 2 \\ 3 & 4 & 4 & 4 \\ 2 & 6 & 7 & 5 \\ 8 & 9 & 5 & 9 \end{pmatrix} = 18\,878 \quad (6)$$

These values further allow the calculation of the permanent index of the CSF as follows

$$CSF = \begin{pmatrix} 15887 & 7 & 6 & 7 & 5 \\ 3 & 18195 & 6 & 5 & 7 \\ 4 & 4 & 13306 & 5 & 4 \\ 3 & 5 & 5 & 11\,256 & 5 \\ 5 & 3 & 6 & 5 & 18878 \end{pmatrix} = 8.17 \times 10^{20} \quad (1)$$

The computed index values of the critical success factors for foreign entrepreneurs are shown in Table 4. The index value of a specific factor shows the extent of its influence on the ability of foreigners to set up profitable businesses in China. Higher index values suggest that a factor has stronger impact on the outcome meanwhile a lower index value suggests relatively weaker impact of that factor.

Table 4. Permanent Index Values

Critical Factor	GP	DG	BR	MC	Fu	TBV	TWV	CSF	TBV for CSF	TWV for CSF
Permanent Index Value	15,887	18,195	13,306	11,256	18,878	33,336	6,776	8.17×10^{20}	4.11×10^{22}	1.43×10^{19}

In order to give meaning and allow for a sort of measurement the calculation of the theoretical best and worst value is necessary. It will also facilitate the estimation of the coefficient of similarity. The theoretical best value (TBV) of the permanent index value, equation 8, is obtained by making the inheritance of the subfactors have the best possible value (in this case 9).

$$\text{Theoretical best value for major factors} = \begin{pmatrix} 9 & 5 & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & 9 & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & 9 & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & 5 & 9 \end{pmatrix} = 33\,336 \quad (8)$$

Meaning the highest possible value of any major factor hypothetically is 33 336.

The theoretical worst value (TWV) of the permanent index value, equation 9, is obtained by making the inheritance of the subfactors have the worst possible value, in this case 1.

$$\text{Theoretical worst value for all the factors} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 5 & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & 1 & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & 1 & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & 5 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = 6\,776 \quad (9)$$

Meaning the lowest possible value of any major factor hypothetically is 6 776.

The coefficient of similarity on the three most important factors was computed. The co-efficient of similarity with best value of a factor connotes the intensity of that factor with the success of foreign entrepreneurs in China Mainland. It is calculated in equation 10, to find how critical these success factors are in comparison to each other as follows:

$$K'_{si} = \frac{W_{ij}-C_{ij}}{W_{ij}-B_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

Where B_{ij} is the best theoretical value

C_{ij} is the permanent index value

W_{ij} is the theoretical worst value

K'_{si} is the co-efficient of similarity compared with the worst value

$$K_{si} \text{ for Funding factor} = \frac{6776-18878}{6776-33336} = 0.46 \quad (10a)$$

$$K_{si} \text{ for Demographics factor} = \frac{6776-18195}{6776-33336} = 0.43 \quad (10b)$$

$$K_{si} \text{ the Government Policy} = \frac{6776-15887}{6776-33336} = 0.34 \quad (10c)$$

Measured on a scale of 0-1, a smaller value shows a weaker intensity of the relationship while a higher value shows a stronger one. This implies that the intensity of the factor F_u , equation 10a, is more critical ($K_{si}=0.46$) to the success of foreign entrepreneurs than that of demographics ($K_{is}=0.43$) although the degree should be noted as small.

Most of the variables presented index values that are closer to the best value than the worst value indicating that the level of influence the factors chosen is above average and their influence on the business outcomes of foreign entrepreneurs is significant.

Findings and Discussion

The CSF index of 8.17×10^{20} out of a possible 4.11×10^{22} shows how important the factors chosen for this study are to the success of foreign-owned businesses setting up shop in China Mainland. The critical success index value is closer to the best value than the worst value also indicating the factors chosen have a significant though not absolute influence on the success of foreign entrepreneurs.

Main Findings

The most critical success factor for foreign entrepreneurs in China is determined to be Funding (F_u : $PI= 18\ 878$), confirming earlier studies (Blachman, 2018; Bo, 2019). Some of the most lucrative foreign owned businesses are actually technology companies which have a tremendous amount of government support in terms of capital and preferential treatment (Bo, 2019; Deloitte, 2017). This result is replicated in the coefficient of similarity ($K_{si}=0.46$). Access to financial capital is therefore the most critical success factor that influences the activity of foreign entrepreneurs in China. While self-organized entrepreneurship is common amongst foreign entrepreneurs in China, (Deloitte, 2017) notes that should a venture be started without at least 1 million RMB, this startup runs the risk of hemorrhaging cash and failing with 3-5 years. This means financial resources are

extremely crucial for foreign entrepreneurs because they cannot easily attain loans and credit instruments from Chinese banks and institutions.

The next most important factor is are the Demographic profile of the country (DG: PI= 18 195) followed by the Government Policies (GP: PI= 15 887). These results stand to back the trends that have been observed by (Goodman, 2008) who described the lucrative large population and wealthy upper- and middle-class consumers that make China such an alluring market to capture. China's population is largely modernized now and has been described as being tech-savvy. Understanding the populations dynamic wants, needs and expectations for products, services and organizational conduct and policies will make firms more attractive to consumers and gain them an advantage over others. And this integration of the Chinese style of service and product delivery, must not be just on face value, it must run throughout the organization, because in China, culture matters (Stoermer, Hildisch, Froese, & Tung, 2016). The central government's recent policies to boost international trade through the BRI and domestic innovative companies also shows how national strategy is bringing about opportunities for foreign entrepreneurs. This supports (Woetzel et al., 2014) who states that the 'most powerful shaping forces' in the business sector in China are government policies and the attractiveness of a huge wealthy population.

One crucial interdependency brought out in this study was that Funding, which has the highest index value, is actually a result of government policies. According to (Deloitte, 2017), government efforts to develop certain geographic regions is the driving force behind funding for foreign entrepreneurs in certain cities and industries including agriculture, software and integrated circuit industries, transfer of technology and environmental enterprises. Even non-government income sources for entrepreneurs such as crowdfunding, venture capital and private equity are all heavily regulated by the central government and state controlled financial institutions. It is only through Government policy that Funding can be attained. This means Government Policy, which drives Funding, is the most crucial factor.

The factors with the lowest index values, Market Competition (13 306) and Business relations (11 256) have little yet still significant influence on the success of foreign entrepreneurs. As more Chinese companies build strong brands that can rival foreign companies, the market has slowly been leveled out, making an almost fair chance to any entrepreneur to capture their customers, if only they can maintain an exceptional level of. Furthermore, market competition has been leveled out over the years and foreign firms have lost that asset of foreignness (Ikegami et al., 2017). Now, product and service quality must appeal to consumers more than other brands to gain a competitive advantage, which requires foreign firms to better understand the market demographic and serve them better. Meanwhile as much of China's business is conducted via the internet and business trading platforms, the versatility of personal relations is slightly diminished and the absence therefore may not be detrimental to business dealings. Therefore, in this digital age, the role of guanxi and social capital still exists but is less and less apparent.

Practical Implications

The authors expect this research to inform on the critical success factors and to explore the exact nature of these factors and their interdependencies. It is clear that not all aspects of the economy or institutional framework have the same amount of influence on the business environment. Looking back, the main contribution of the paper was to find out market entry for foreigners in China remained difficult. With Funding and Government policies coming out on top, it is imperial that entrepreneurs align their businesses, innovations and creations according to ongoing national strategies and policies. This can help not only to receive special considerations, build much needed vertical ties but will also avoid unpredictable and sudden policy changes that may work against the entrepreneurs. Much of the government strategies for business and entrepreneurs is available publicly sometimes in English but mostly in Chinese. Aspiring and current entrepreneurs looking to enter or further penetrate the Chinese market are encouraged to use this research to better understand their options and gain competitive advantage, meanwhile not taking the CSFs into considerations may hinder growth of their ventures.

Decision-makers and entrepreneurs can get direction from the findings stated here and frame informed plans and business tactics to consider these factors. These critical success factors are not only helpful for identifying the best course of action but also to help choose the industries to enter as well as how best to ameliorate current business practices. As China becomes a battleground where innovative entrepreneurs fight for market share, entrepreneurs should build highly specialized skills and products and services that can rival not only domestic offerings but also other foreign counterparts. The Government Policies are geared towards recruiting top tier talent while Funding and Demographics will be drawn towards new products and brands that exhibit exquisite craftsmanship in quality, design, offering and delivery. Entrepreneurs who need Funding, that is technology entrepreneurs and self-organized entrepreneurs must enter the STEM fields to benefit from tax holidays and business incubation and acceleration programs. They must also choose cities that can offer them skilled talent and access to other government funded programs and VCs. In summary, there are countless opportunities that have been offered to foreign entrepreneurs and in this paper an outline of what factors can be exploited to take full advantage of these opportunities are explained.

Conclusion

Notwithstanding its impressive economic development, China is still a transitional economy, as it is arguably still moving from a position where few market supporting institutions existed. Thus, it may still be problematic to apply management approaches from advanced Western countries in China. Most foreigners in China yearn to capitalize on the enabling business environment to actualize their business ideas by building new companies or enterprises, but obstacles constrain them daily. Despite the challenges, there are other major success factors promoting foreign entrepreneurship. Perhaps the challenges are not what to expect but the persistent efforts by entrepreneurs to rise out of all odds through the success factors. The findings of the study have revealed numerous factors influencing the foreign entrepreneurial front. These factors seem to be cutting across all forms of entrepreneurship. Finally, what are the critical success factors for foreign entrepreneurs doing business in China? Evidence from literature and established entrepreneurs (experts' opinion) points to the government policies of China, funding

opportunities and demographic make-up of the population present the strongest influences.

Therefore, to create a genuine enterprise in China and enhancing the influencing factors of foreign entrepreneurs, new and growing businesses need to consider government policies on entrepreneurship, access to finance and the demographic structure of the populace. Particularly, Government policies actively promoted new and growing entrepreneurial firms with funding for new and growing companies that focus on prioritized portfolios. Entrepreneurs can carefully navigate these factors to get the niche market they can flourish in. Within these factors it was found that establishing startups in government supported and funded industries such a technology, targeting products for upper- and middle-class consumers, locating within 1st and 2nd tier cities and taking advantage of online business will give foreign entrepreneurs the greatest opportunities.

Limitations and areas for further study

This study outlined 20 factors that influence the entrepreneur's establishment in China. China has one of the biggest economies and has much potentials for foreign entrepreneurs as such it makes it significant for research study of this kind. It is entirely possible that there are other factors that were not accounted for, because the experience of each entrepreneur is different. Future research may consider more subfactors and major factors, subsystems that can consider more factors and develop a more comprehensive model. The use of GTMA in this study shows the efficacy of combinatorial mathematics in understanding complex social issues. Going further, research can make us of simulation models such and agent-based modelling or systems dynamic to better understand the behavioral patterns of foreign entrepreneurs in China, and add to the research on transnational entrepreneurs.

References

- Abubakar, A. M., Anasori, E., & Lasisi, T. T. (2019). Physical attractiveness and managerial favoritism in the hotel industry: The light and dark side of erotic capital. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 38, 16-26.
- Agrawal, S., Singh, R. K., & Murtaza, Q. (2016). Outsourcing decisions in reverse logistics: Sustainable balanced scorecard and graph theoretic approach. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 108, 41-53.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.01.004>
- Ahlstrom, D., & Ding, Z. (2015). Entrepreneurship in China: Progress and Challenges *Developments in Chinese Entrepreneurship* (pp. 1-32): Springer.
- Ahlstrom, D., Young, M. N., Nair, A., & Law, P. (2003). Managing the institutional environment: Challenges for foreign firms in post WTO China. *SAM Advanced Management Journal*, 68(2), 41-49.
- Alvarez, S. A., Barney, J. B., & Anderson, P. (2013). Forming and exploiting opportunities: The implications of discovery and creation processes for

- entrepreneurial and organizational research. *Organization science*, 24(1), 301-317.
doi:doi/abs/10.1287/orsc.1110.0727
- Anwar, S., & Sun, S. (2015). Foreign direct investment in R&D and domestic entrepreneurship in China's manufacturing industries. *Applied Economics*, 47(16), 1633-1651.
- Arribas, I., Hernández, P., & Vila, J. E. (2013). , performance and innovation in entrepreneurial service projects. *Management Decision*, 51(1), 173-183.
doi:10.1108/00251741311291373
- Ashourizadeh, S., Li, J., & Wickstrøm, K. A. (2020). Immigrants Entrepreneurial Networks and Export: A Comparative Study. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 1-28. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-020-00665-y>
- Benzing, C., Chu, H. M., & Kara, O. (2009). Entrepreneurs in Turkey: A factor analysis of motivations, success factors, and problems. *Journal of small business management*, 47(1), 58-91.
- Bick, R., Chang, M., Wang, K. W., & Yu, T. (2020). A blueprint for remote working: Lessons from China. *McKinsey Digital*.
- Blachman, R. (2018). China-Israel Innovation Accelerator. *VentureBeat.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/venturebeat.com/2018/12/01/chinas-vcs-show-new-interest-in-backing-foreign-bred-startups/amp/>
- Bo, J. (2019). Amid Tradewar, foreign startups may spot opportunity in China. Retrieved from <https://venturebeat.com/2019/03/16/amid-trade-war-foreign-startups-may-spot-opportunity-in-china/amp/>
- Buyse, K., & Essers, D. (2019). Cheating tiger, tech-savvy dragon: Are Western concerns about “unfair trade” and “Made in China 2025” justified? *Economic Review*(ii), 47-70.
- CambridgeDictionary. (Ed.) (2021).
- Chandra, A., & Fealey, T. (2009). Business incubation in the United States, China and Brazil: A comparison of role of government, incubator funding and financial services. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 13, 67.
- Chang, V. K., & Pieke, F. N. (2018). Europe's engagement with China: shifting Chinese views of the EU and the EU-China relationship. *Asia Europe Journal*, 16(4), 317-331.
- Chang, Y., & Hu, J. (2020). Analysis on the Mode of Multinational Retail Enterprises Entering Chinese Market—Take Walmart, Carrefour and Metro as Examples. *Modern Economy*, 11(01), 17. doi:10.4236/me.2020.111003

- Chua, R. Y. J., Ingram, P., & Morris, M. W. (2008). From the head and the heart: Locating cognition-and affect-based trust in managers' professional networks. *Academy of Management journal*, 51(3), 436-452.
- Collinson, S., & Liu, Y. (2019). Recombination for innovation: performance outcomes from international partnerships in China. *R&D Management*, 49(1), 46-63. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/radm.12293>
- Cui, L., & Kwon, J.-W. (2014). Types of Language Usage and Language Barrier Solutions for MNCs in China. *한국국제경영관리학회 학술발표대회 논문집*, 553-572.
- Deloitte. (2017). *Taxation and Investment in China*. Retrieved from <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/global/Documents/Tax/dttl-tax-chinaguide-2017.pdf>
- Devi, R. M. (2020). Eco-Friendly Entrepreneur-a Beacon Light to Green India; Dream India.". *Our Heritage*, 68(1), 6549-6554.
- Dickson, R. S., Yao, D., & Hill, I. L. (2020). A Study on the Challenges and Opportunities Faced by Foreign Entrepreneurs in China. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 8(04), 1684.
- Fan, Z., & Zhang, R. (2017). Financial inclusion, entry barriers, and entrepreneurship: evidence from China. *Sustainability*, 9(2), 203. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su9020203>
- Fang, T., Tung, R. L., Berg, L., & Nematshahi, N. (2017). Parachuting internationalization: a study of four Scandinavian firms entering China. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*.
- Farrell, D., Gersch, U. A., & Stephenson, E. (2006). The value of China's emerging middle class. *McKinsey Quarterly*, 2(1), 60.
- Froese, F. J., Sutherland, D., Lee, J. Y., Liu, Y., & Pan, Y. (2019). Challenges for foreign companies in China: implications for research and practice. *Asian Business & Management*, 18(4), 249-262. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41291-019-00084-0>
- Goodman, D. (2008). *The new rich in China: Future rulers, present lives*: Routledge.
- Grover, S., Agrawal, V., & Khan, I. (2004). A digraph approach to TQM evaluation of an industry. *International Journal of Production Research*, 42(19), 4031-4053. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/00207540410001704032>
- Gupta, T. K., & Singh, V. (2015). A systematic approach to evaluate supply chain management environment index using graph theoretic approach. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management*, 21(1), 1-45.

- Gurău, C., Dana, L.-P., & Katz-Volovelsky, E. (2020). Spanning transnational boundaries in industrial markets: A study of Israeli entrepreneurs in China. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 89, 389-401.
- Gurumurthy, A., Mazumdar, P., & Muthusubramanian, S. (2013). Graph theoretic approach for analysing the readiness of an organisation for adapting lean thinking: A case study. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 21(3), 396-427. doi:10.1108/IJOA-04-2013-0652
- Hamizah, A. H. (2020). Challenges experienced by immigrant entrepreneurs in a developing non-Western country: Malaysia. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 8(3), 7-25.
- Harary, F. (1959). Graph Theoretic Methods in the Management Sciences. *Management Science*, 5(4), 387-403. doi:10.1287/mnsc.5.4.387
- He, C., Lu, J., & Qian, H. (2019). Entrepreneurship in China. *Small Business Economics*, 52(3), 563-572.
- Hennessy, K. (2012). Cultural heritage on the web: Applied digital visual anthropology and local cultural property rights discourse. *IJCP*, 19, 345.
- Huang, Q., Liu, X., & Li, J. (2016). Entrepreneurship in China. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development: Special Issue*, 28(9-10), 817-819. doi:https://doi.org/10.1080/08985626.2017.1251140
- Ikegami, J. J., Maznevski, M., & Ota, M. (2017). Creating the asset of foreignness: Schrödinger's cat and lessons from the Nissan revival. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*.
- Jayaraman, K. (2010). Doing business in China: A risk analysis. *Journal of Emerging Knowledge on Emerging Markets*, 1(1), 7. doi:https://doi.org/10.7885/1946-651X.1006
- Ji-yun, H. (2002). The Analysis on the Recent-year Reforms of China's Foreign Currency Control System. *South China Financial Research*.
- Jiang, L., & Shan, J. (2016). Counterfeits or Shanzhai? The role of face and brand consciousness in luxury copycat consumption. *Psychological Reports*, 119(1), 181-199.
- Kaplan, S. N., & Stromberg, P. (2009). Leveraged buyouts and private equity. *Journal of economic perspectives*, 23(1), 121-146. doi:10.1257/jep.23.1.121
- Karadal, H., Shneikat, B. H. T., Abubakar, A. M., & Bhatti, O. K. (2020). Immigrant Entrepreneurship: the Case of Turkish Entrepreneurs in the United States. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1-20.

- Karakaya, F., & Stahl, M. J. (1989). Barriers to entry and market entry decisions in consumer and industrial goods markets. *Journal of marketing*, 53(2), 80-91.
- Kloosterman, R. C. (2010). Matching opportunities with resources: A framework for analysing (migrant) entrepreneurship from a mixed embeddedness perspective. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 22(1), 25-45.
- Lee, M. (2003). Franchising in China: Legal Challenges When First Entering the Chinese Market. *American University. Int'l Law. Review.*, 19, 949.
- Lerner, J., & Schoar, A. (2005). Does legal enforcement affect financial transactions? The contractual channel in private equity. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 120(1), 223-246. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1162/0033553053327443>
- Li, K., Zhang, Y., Wang, W., Jiang, Y., & Zhang, H. (2021). Spatial location of new foreign firms in Shanghai under the transformation of urban development. *Bulletin of Economic Research*, n/a(n/a). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/boer.12300>
- Li, M., He, L., & Zhao, Y. (2020). The triple helix system and regional entrepreneurship in China. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 32(7-8), 508-530. doi:[10.1080/08985626.2019.1666168](https://doi.org/10.1080/08985626.2019.1666168)
- Lightfoot, W. S., & Almeida, J. (2007). Leveraging knowledge in China: the experience of a foreign entrepreneur. *Journal of Technology Management in China*.
- Liu, K., Al Asady, A., & Fu, K. (2020). How do foreign entrepreneurs adapt to local corruption norms in the Middle East? Institutional multiplicities and individual adaptation. *International Small Business Journal*, 38(7), 629-653. doi:[10.1177/0266242620918823](https://doi.org/10.1177/0266242620918823)
- Lukes, M., & Stephan, U. (2012). Nonprofit leaders and for-profit entrepreneurs: Similar people with different motivation. *Ceskoslovenska psychologie*, 56(1), 41-55.
- Luo, X., & Lemański, M. K. (2016). FDI strategies of Chinese companies in the electronics industry: Motives, locations, and entry mode choices *The challenge of bric multinationals*: Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Min, H., & Chen, G. (2003). *Challenges and opportunities for entering the Chinese logistics market*. Paper presented at the Supply Chain Forum: An International Journal.
- Mitchell, J. R., Mitchell, R. K., & Randolph-Seng, B. (2014). *Handbook of Entrepreneurial Cognition*: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Mitchell, R., Randolph-Seng, B., & Mitchell, J. (2011). Socially Situated Cognition: Imagining New Opportunities for Entrepreneurship Research. *Academy of management review*, 36, 774-776. doi:[10.5465/amr.2011.0001](https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2011.0001)

- Mitchell, R. K., Smith, B., Seawright, K. W., & Morse, E. A. (2000). Cross-Cultural Cognitions and the Venture Creation Decision. *Academy of Management journal*, 43(5), 974-993. doi:10.5465/1556422
- Mitchell, R. K., Smith, J. B., Morse, E. A., Seawright, K. W., Peredo, A. M., & McKenzie, B. (2002). Are Entrepreneurial Cognitions Universal? Assessing Entrepreneurial Cognitions across Cultures. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 26(4), 9-32. doi:10.1177/104225870202600402
- MofCom. (2018). *Foreign Investment Statistics*. Retrieved from <http://english.mofcom.gov.cn/article/statistic/foreigninvestment/>.
- Muduli, K., Govindan, K., Barve, A., & Geng, Y. (2013). Barriers to green supply chain management in Indian mining industries: a graph theoretic approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 47, 335-344.
- Munganyi, T. (2020, 6 February 2020) *Doing business in China/Interviewer: B. Madzikanda*. Research, Shanghai, China.
- Nazareno, J., Zhou, M., & You, T. (2019). Global dynamics of immigrant entrepreneurship: Changing trends, ethnonational variations, and reconceptualizations. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 25(5), 780-800. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-03-2018-0141>
- NBS. (2021). China National Bureau of Statistics. <http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/>
- NBSC. (2010). China statistical yearbook. In N. B. o. S. o. China (Ed.): National Bureau of Statistics of China Beijing.
- NBSC. (2019). *China Statistical Year Book*. Retrieved from <http://www.stats.gov.cn/enGLISH/>.
- Ng, K. S., & Fu, P. P. (2018). Factors driving foreign women entrepreneurship in China. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 6(4), 49.
- Niu, Y., Dong, L. C., & Chen, R. (2012). Market entry barriers in China. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(1), 68-76. doi:[doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.01.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.01.018)
- North, D. C. (1991). Institutions. *Journal of economic perspectives*, 5(1), 97-112.
- Park, B. I., & Xiao, S. (2021). Doing good by combating bad in the digital world: Institutional pressures, anti-corruption practices, and competitive implications of MNE foreign subsidiaries. *Journal of Business Research*, 137, 194-205. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.08.014>
- Park, S. H., & Ungson, G. R. (2016). Blind spots in global strategy: applications in emerging markets. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*.

- Park, S. H., Ungson, G. R., & Zhou, N. (2013). *Rough diamonds: The four traits of successful breakout firms in BRIC countries*: John Wiley & Sons.
- Pellegrini, M. M., & Ciappei, C. (2015). Ethical judgment and radical business changes: the role of entrepreneurial perspicacity. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 128(4), 769-788.
- Phillips, N., & Tracey, P. (2007). Opportunity recognition, entrepreneurial capabilities and bricolage: connecting institutional theory and entrepreneurship in strategic organization. *Strategic organization*, 5(3), 313-320.
doi:10.1177/1476127007079956
- Puslecki, L., Trapczynski, P., & Staszaków, M. (2016). Emerging advanced topics in an advanced emerging market? International business research in Poland in the period 1990-2014. *Journal of East European Management Studies*, 21(2), 139-166.
- Qi, F., Wu, Y., Wang, J., & Wang, Q. (2021). China's Hainan Free Trade Port: Medical Laws and Policy Reform. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9(1783).
doi:10.3389/fpubh.2021.764977
- Qian, H. (2017). Knowledge base differentiation in urban systems of innovation and entrepreneurship. *Urban Studies*, 54(7), 1655-1672.
doi:doi.org/10.1177/0042098016629314
- Raeesi, R., Dastranj, M., Mohammadi, S., & Rasouli, E. (2013). Understanding the interactions among the barriers to entrepreneurship using interpretive structural modeling. *international Journal of Business and Management*, 8(13), 56.
- Randolph-Seng, B., Mitchell, R. K., Vahidnia, H., Mitchell, J. R., Chen, S., & Statzer, J. (2015). The Microfoundations of Entrepreneurial Cognition Research: Toward an Integrative Approach. *Foundations and Trends® in Entrepreneurship*, 11(4), 207-335. doi:10.1561/03000000055
- Randolph-Seng, J. S. C., & Atinc, Y. (2020). Dynamic entrepreneurial cognition: current trends and future opportunities. *Management Decision*, 58(7), 1237-1246.
- Raza, A., Muffatto, M., & Saeed, S. (2018). Cross-country differences in innovative entrepreneurial activity: An entrepreneurial cognitive view. *Management Decision*.
- Riege, A. M. (2003). Validity and reliability tests in case study research: a literature review with “hands-on” applications for each research phase. *Qualitative market research: An international journal*.
- Sanchez, J., Carballo, T., & Gutiérrez, A. (2011). The entrepreneur from a cognitive approach. *Psicothema*, 23, 433-438.

- Sarasvathy, S., & Dew, N. (2011). Without judgment: An empirically-based entrepreneurial theory of the firm. *The Review of Austrian Economics*, 26. doi:10.1007/s11138-011-0170-4
- Sassetti, S., Marzi, G., Cavaliere, V., & Ciappei, C. (2018). Entrepreneurial cognition and socially situated approach: a systematic and bibliometric analysis. *Scientometrics*, 116(3), 1675-1718.
- Shan, S., Jia, Y., Zheng, X., & Xu, X. (2018). Assessing relationship and contribution of China's technological entrepreneurship to socio-economic development. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 135, 83-90. doi:doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2017.12.022
- Shepherd, D., & Patzelt, H. (2018). *Entrepreneurial Cognition*.
- Si, Y., Zhang, Y., & Teng, T. (2021). R&D internationalization and innovation performance of Chinese enterprises: The mediating role of returnees and foreign professionals. *Growth and Change*, 52(4), 2194-2212. doi:https://doi.org/10.1111/grow.12555
- St-Jean, E., & Audet, J. (2012). The role of mentoring in the learning development of the novice entrepreneur. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 8(1), 119-140.
- St-Jean, É., & Duhamel, M. (2020). Employee work–life balance and work satisfaction: an empirical study of entrepreneurial career transition and intention across 70 different economies. *Academia Revista Latinoamericana de Administracion*. doi:doi.org/10.1108/ARLA-02-2019-0054
- Steinz, H. J., Van Rijnsoever, F. J., & Nauta, F. (2016). How to Green the red Dragon: A Start-ups' Little Helper for Sustainable Development in China. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 25(8), 593-608.
- Stephan, U., Hart, M., & Drews, C.-C. (2015). Understanding motivations for entrepreneurship: A review of recent research evidence: Enterprise Research Centre.
- Stoermer, S., Hildisch, A. K., Froese, F. J., & Tung, R. (2016). Culture matters: The influence of national culture on inclusion climate. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*.
- Sydler, R., Haefliger, S., & Pruksa, R. (2014). Measuring intellectual capital with financial figures: Can we predict firm profitability? *European Management Journal*, 32(2), 244-259.
- Trimarchi, M., Liesch, P. W., & Tamaschke, R. (2010). A study of compatibility variation across Chinese buyer-seller relationships. *European Journal of Marketing*. doi:doi.org/10.1108/03090561011008628

- Tung, S., & Cho, S. (2000). The impact of tax incentives on foreign direct investment in China. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 9(2), 105-135.
- Urban, B., Van Vuuren, J., & Barreira, J. (2008). High-growth entrepreneurs: the relevance of business knowledge and work experience on venture success. *Journal of Contemporary Management*, 5(1), 58-71. doi:
<https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC51032>
- Urbano, D., Audretsch, D., Aparicio, S., & Noguera, M. (2019). Does entrepreneurial activity matter for economic growth in developing countries? The role of the institutional environment. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 1-35. doi:doi.org/10.1007/s11365-019-00621-5
- Venkataraman, S. (2019). The distinctive domain of entrepreneurship research *Seminal ideas for the next twenty-five years of advances*: Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Verot, O. (2018). Key factors of success for a foreign company in China. Retrieved from MarketingtoChina.com
- Wach, D., Stephan, U., & Gorgievski, M. (2016). More than money: Developing an integrative multi-factorial measure of entrepreneurial success. *International Small Business Journal*, 34(8), 1098-1121.
- Wach, D., Stephan, U., Marjan, J. G., & Wegge, J. (2018). Entrepreneurs' achieved success: developing a multi-faceted measure. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 1-29. doi:doi.org/10.1007/s11365-018-0532-5
- Wang, P., Kinnucan, H. W., & Duffy, P. A. (2019). The effects of rising labour costs on global supply chains: the case of China's cotton yarn industry. *Applied Economics*, 51(33), 3608-3623.
- Woetzel, J., Orr, G., Lau, A., Chen, Y., Chang, E., Seong, J., . . . Qiu, A. (2014). China's digital transformation: The Internet's impact on productivity and growth. *McKinsey Global Institute, July, McKinsey&Company*.
- Worldwide, A. (2010). China's 12th Five-Year Plan: How it actually works and what's in store for the next five years. *December, 10, 2*.
- Wu, C., & Burge, G. S. (2018). Competing for foreign direct investment: The case of local governments in China. *Public Finance Review*, 46(6), 1044-1068.
- Xu, D., Pan, Y., Wu, C., & Yim, B. (2006). Performance of domestic and foreign-invested enterprises in China. *Journal of World Business*, 41(3), 261-274. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2005.10.002>
- Yang, D. T., Chen, V. W., & Monarch, R. (2010). Rising wages: Has China lost its global labor advantage? *Pacific Economic Review*, 15(4), 482-504.

- Yang, L. (2015). Empirical study on the relationship between entrepreneurial cognitions and strategic change momentum. *Management Decision*, 53(5), 957-983. doi:10.1108/MD-10-2014-0602
- Yau, O. H., Lee, J. S., Chow, R. P., Sin, L. Y., & Alan, C. (2000). Relationship marketing the Chinese way. *Business Horizons*, 43(1), 16-16. doi:doi.org/10.1016/S0007-6813(00)87383-8
- Yen, D. A.-w., & Abosag, I. (2016). Localization in China: How guanxi moderates Sino-US business relationships. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(12), 5724-5734.
- York, J. G., & Venkataraman, S. (2010). The entrepreneur-environment nexus: Uncertainty, innovation, and allocation. *Journal of business venturing*, 25(5), 449-463.
- Zanella, G., Solano, D. B. C., Hallam, C. R., & Guda, T. (2019). The role of the organization in the entrepreneur-opportunity nexus. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*.
- Zhang, W., & Zhai, Y. (2016). *SME's Entry Process in Emerging Markets-A case study of the Nordgröna AB entering Chinese Market*. (Master's), Lund University. Retrieved from <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/8887235> (8887235)
- Zhang, Y., Zhao, W., & Ge, J. (2016). Institutional duality and political strategies of foreign-invested firms in an emerging economy. *Journal of World Business*, 51(3), 451-462. doi:/doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2015.12.004
- Zheng, T., Zhao, Y., & Li, J. (2019). Rising labour cost, environmental regulation and manufacturing restructuring of Chinese cities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 214, 583-592.
- Zhou, D. (2012). Chinese entrepreneurs go global. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 2(2).

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